

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	114992 (2020 round)
Principle Investigator	Adrian Sanchez Fernandez
Structure/Description	
Code	AEL03059
Producer	Anna Leung
Mass	372 mg
% Deuteration	Non-deuterated
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of palmitoleoyl- β -D-maltopyranoside (400 MHz, CD_3OD).

Figure 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of palmitoleoyl- β -D-maltopyranoside (100 MHz, CD_3OD).